

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF FACILITIES CONSTRUCTED ON ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION

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ОЦЕНКА ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ СТРОЯЩИХСЯ ОБЪЕКТОВ НА ЗАГРЯЗНЕНИЕ ОКРУЖАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДЫ

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Abstract

In modern conditions, construction sites around the world have a significant impact on the environment both locally and globally. Every stage of the construction process has a noticeable impact on the environment. This includes the extraction of materials, their transportation from different parts of the world to the construction site, the construction process itself, and waste disposal at the end of construction. In a rapidly evolving global economy, it is critical to understand how projects under construction impact the environment and how this impact can be measured and reduced in the future. This article describes the impact of construction projects on the environment and what measures are needed to reduce this impact.

Аннотация

В современных условиях объекты строительного сектора во всем мире оказывают значительное воздействие на окружающую среду как на местном, так и на глобальном уровне. Каждый этап строительного процесса оказывает заметное воздействие на окружающую среду. Это и добыча материалов, и их транспортировка из разных уголков мира на строительную площадку, и сам процесс строительства, и утилизация отходов по окончании строительства. В условиях быстро развивающейся мировой экономики крайне важно понимать, как строящиеся объекты влияют на окружающую среду и как это влияние можно измерить и уменьшить в будущем. В данной статье описывается воздействие строительных объектов на окружающую среду и то, какие необходимы мероприятия для снижением этого воздействия.

Keywords: construction, object, environment, ecology, factors, building materials.

Ключевые слова: строительство, объект, окружающая среда, экология, факторы, строительные материалы.

In modern conditions, construction is one of the most important sectors of the economy. In addition to the construction of residential buildings, which provide housing for a huge number of the population, it includes the construction of the infrastructure of settlements, the laying of various types of communications, the increase in industrial, agricultural and military facilities, as well as water and hydraulic structures. Construction and related industrial enterprises have a direct impact on the surrounding ecosystem, and this impact is dramatically increasing. Any construction project requires a large amount of mineral raw materials, such as wood, crushed stone, stone, clay and sand. In this regard,

large-scale deforestation and open-pit mining are occurring all over the world, which has an extremely negative impact on the environment. As a result of mining, air and water bodies are polluted, many plants and animals die, and biological and geological ecosystems are disrupted. Active environmental pollution occurs during the processing of resources at industrial enterprises involved in the production of building materials. [5 p.160].

During the production of building materials, a large amount of waste is generated, a large amount of pollutants dust, soot, and gases are released. The construction materials enterprises themselves occupy a

large area, and as a result of construction work, its natural environment is destroyed. The development of construction sites, including the destruction of vegetation and soil cover, causes destructive changes in existing ecosystems. This is because in extreme environmental conditions, recovery can take decades to centuries, and in some cases may never fully recover. In addition to water and air pollution, soil destruction and vegetation destruction, construction work can lead to changes or destruction of seasonal migration routes of animals and fish. The nature of the relationship between the environment and future objects is determined at the building design stage. [4].

When constructing real estate at a certain stage, it is important to take into account the environmental feasibility of construction and possible environmental risks. Designing a construction project without taking into account environmental requirements will subsequently lead to an increase in financial costs for restoring the environment damaged as a result of construction. In developed Western countries, building using local natural building materials and green building using processes and facilities with minimal environmental impact are becoming increasingly popular. In Azerbaijan, "green" construction is just beginning to develop, so many measures for the interaction of construction projects and processes with the surrounding natural ecosystem are advisory in nature. However, for these recommendations to be of real benefit, they must be included in professional regulations and developed with the input of a variety of building and environmental experts. [7 p.52].

Many scientists have made a huge contribution to the study of problems of assessing the impact of objects under construction on the environment [7,8,10]. The results of these scientific studies make it possible to examine in detail the sources of environmental pollution, identify factors and assess the economic damage from urban pollution and methods for its compensation.

At each level of construction of the facility, one of the basic environmental requirements must be observed - the preservation of natural relief and vegetation cover. Therefore, the main criteria for assessing the environmental situation in the development area are: taking into account environmental components; taking into account the health status of the population; state of change in the natural environment, including the natural ecosystem. As a result of the study, it was established that when planning and development projects, environmental factors can be considered in two aspects: 1) creating comfortable conditions for the life of people in the city;

2) regulation of the condition, protection and environmental safety of the environment. When developing construction design documentation, it is only necessary to justify the planned economic or other activities of the future construction site. Therefore, at the investment justification stage, the goal of constructing a facility is to show the possibility of its implementation taking into account certain environmental problems associated with both the regional characteristics of the territory.

It should be noted that when developing the "Environmental Protection" section of the design documentation for a construction project, the following data is taken into account:

1. Brief information about the designed object
2. Protection and rational use of land resources
3. Protection of the air basin in the area where the facility is located from pollution
4. Protection of surface and groundwater from depletion and pollution
5. Environmental protection during storage (disposal) of industrial waste
6. Protection of flora and fauna
7. Forecast of changes in the state of the environment under the influence of the designed facility.

Based on the assessment of these data, an environmental justification for the construction project is given.

The impact of a facility under construction on the environment occurs both during the construction period itself, since it requires a sufficient amount of raw materials, building materials, energy, water and other resources, and during the operation of the constructed facility.

The main factors polluting the environment during the construction phase include:

1. Increase in the amount of construction waste, air pollution during the organization of a construction site
2. Pollution of surface runoff, soil erosion as a result of transportation of construction waste and unloading and loading operations;
3. Increased emissions of harmful substances (gases, dust) into the environment during welding, insulation, roofing and finishing work.
4. Generation of waste and the possibility of dust in the air, vibration and noise loads during stone and concrete work.
5. Shading of areas where development is taking place, which leads to a shortage of solar color necessary for life.
6. Excessive use of energy resources;
7. Locations become less resistant to earthquakes.

Table 1

Generation of construction waste during construction activities (thousand tons)

	2015	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Generation of construction waste	3,3	2,9	3,1	2,1	43,8	5,2
Application and disposal of construction waste	0,6	1,3	1,3	0,8	1,2	1,2

As can be seen from Table 1, the sharp increase in construction waste in recent years creates an additional

burden on the environment. At the same time, the possibility of their secondary use is insignificant every year [1,2.p. 79-80].

In addition, after construction is completed, new problems arise during the operation of buildings, such as poor lighting, soil pollution, a decrease in the amount of vegetation, and thermal pollution.

To solve the problems of improving the environmental and social consequences of the construction and operation of construction projects, a multifactorial

model of the need to conduct economic analysis is presented, thereby reducing the negative consequences of the construction project on the environment. [4].

As can be seen from Figure 1, economic analysis and problem solving will create favorable conditions for the construction and operation of the facility.

Fig. 1. Economic analysis of the impact of a construction project on the environment.

Conclusions: to prevent adverse effects on the environment during the construction of facilities, it is necessary to carry out such measures as: organizing a waste collection site; garbage removal in closed bodies; organization of proper storage and transportation of flammable materials; organization of wastewater treatment; processing of materials in dust collection devices; fencing and replanting of preserved trees and others.

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